

Serum Interferon Gamma (IFN- γ) Levels and Hematological Indices in Patients with HIV-MTB Co-Infection in North-Eastern Nigeria

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Abstract:

Introduction: The dual epidemic of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection and Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) poses significant health challenges, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Understanding the immune response and hematological changes in HIV-MTB co-infection is crucial for better management of affected individuals. **Objectives:** This study aimed to evaluate the serum levels of IFN- γ and hematological indices in patients with HIV-MTB co-infection in North-Eastern Nigeria, as well as explore any potential relationships between these factors. **Methods:** A total of 88 participants were enrolled in the study, including 44 antiretroviral therapy-naive patients with HIV-MTB

co-infection (study group) and 44 HIV mono-infected individuals as controls. Data on personal biodata and clinical details were collected using an interviewer-administered questionnaire. Blood samples were obtained from each participant and analyzed for IFN- γ levels using ELISA and hematological indices using an automated hematology analyzer. Statistical analysis, including Mann-Whitney U test, independent samples t-test, and Pearson's correlation analysis, was conducted to compare the study and control groups and assess the relationship between IFN- γ levels and hematological parameters. **Results:** Serum IFN- γ was insignificantly increased in the study group compared to the control group ($p=0.093$). The WBC count was also significantly reduced in the study group compared to the control group ($p=0.038$). The HGB, HCT, MCV and MCH were significantly reduced in the study group compared to

the control group ($p=0.001, 0.001, 0.002$ and 0.001) respectively. Participants with HIV-TB co-infection have insignificantly increased serum IFN- γ levels, low total WBC, lymphocyte and monocyte counts compared to those with HIV mono-infection. In conclusion, participants with HIV-TB co-infection have insignificant increased serum IFN- γ levels, low total WBC, and lymphocyte and monocyte counts compared to those with HIV mono-infection. There was no correlation of IFN- γ with any of the haematological indices.

Keywords: *HIV, Mycobacterium tuberculosis, co-infection, interferon gamma, hematological indices.*

Introduction

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) infections are major global health concerns, particularly in developing countries. The co-infection of HIV and tuberculosis (TB) is a significant challenge, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. TB ranks as the second leading cause of death from an infectious disease worldwide, following HIV. In Nigeria, the proportion of TB/HIV co-infected patients is considerable, and these individuals often experience poorer treatment outcomes. HIV infection significantly increases the susceptibility to and progression of TB, even before a decrease in CD4⁺ T-cell counts below a certain threshold. The increased susceptibility to active TB in HIV-infected individuals is multifactorial and extends beyond CD4⁺ T-cell depletion. Understanding the immunological factors involved in this co-infection is crucial (Mohan et al., 2001; Maartens and Wilkinson, 2007; Daniel et al., 2006; WHO, 2005; Sonnenberg, 2005; Cooper et al., 2008; Schroder et al., 2004).

Interferon gamma (IFN- γ) plays a crucial role in the immune response against mycobacterial infections. It activates macrophages, enhances antigen presentation, and promotes the differentiation of CD4⁺ T lymphocytes to the Th1 subpopulation. IFN- γ induces the transcription of various genes involved in antimicrobial functions, making it an essential effector mechanism against Mycobacterium tuberculosis (Cooper, 2009; Oberholzer et al., 2000). IFN- γ production is decreased in HIV-infected individuals, which can contribute to the impaired control of MTB infection and disease progression. The dysregulation of IFN- γ

production in HIV-infected individuals is associated with chronic immune activation and the excessive production of type-1 interferon (IFN) by plasmacytoid dendritic cells. This dysregulation may further contribute to the impaired control of MTB infection and disease progression (Fitzgerald-Bocarsly et al., 2010).

The importance of IFN- γ in controlling M. tuberculosis infection has been demonstrated in both experimental and clinical studies. Mice with a disrupted IFN- γ gene show increased susceptibility to tuberculosis, and reintroduction of this gene into the lung confers resistance. Similar observations have been made in macaque monkeys and humans with high IFN- γ levels who are more likely to develop active tuberculosis (Moreira et al., 2000; Lin et al., 2009). Additionally, individuals with mutations in genes of the IL-12/IL-23/IFN- γ axis exhibit increased susceptibility to mycobacterial infections (Al-Musen and Casanova, 2006).

Anemia is a common complication in both TB and HIV infections and is associated with increased morbidity and mortality. Factors contributing to anemia in these infections include decreased red blood cell production, malabsorption syndrome, and nutritional deficiencies (Johnson et al., 2006; Belperio and Rhew, 2004). The affected hematological indices include packed cell volume (PCV), thrombocytes, total and differential counts, with neutropenia, lymphopenia, and thrombocytopenia as common features (Johnson et al., 2006).

The high burden of TB/HIV co-infections in African and Asian countries poses significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges, placing

immense pressure on healthcare systems. Therefore, understanding the host immune response to this co-infection is crucial for improving management strategies (Getahun et al., 2010).

Therefore the objective of this study was to evaluate the serum levels of IFN- γ and hematological indices in patients with HIV-MTB co-infection in North-Eastern Nigeria. Additionally, we aimed to explore any relationships between serum IFN- γ levels and hematological parameters in these patients.

Study Design

This study employed a cross-sectional design. Participants were enrolled from the antiretroviral therapy (ART) clinic of FMC Yola, Adamawa, Nigeria. Two groups were included: a study group consisting of antiretroviral therapy-naïve patients with HIV-MTB co-infection, and a control group comprising HIV mono-infected individuals. A total of 88 participants were enrolled, with 44 participants in each group.

Data Collection and Laboratory Analysis: Personal biodata and clinical details were collected using an interviewer-administered questionnaire. Five milliliters of venous blood samples were collected from each participant, with 4 milliliters collected in EDTA BD Vacutainer tubes for hematological analysis. The remaining samples in plain containers were separated, aliquoted into vials containing aprotinin, and stored at -70°C until batch analysis of IFN- γ using ELISA. Hematological indices, including white blood cells (WBCs), platelets, PCV, and neutrophils, were determined using an automated hematology analyzer.

Ethical Considerations: This study obtained ethical approval from the Health Research Ethical Committees of Federal Medical Center, Yola. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring confidentiality and the freedom to withdraw from the study.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were subjected to normality tests. Haematological data were summarized using mean and standard deviation, while IFN- γ levels were summarized

using median and interquartile range. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare IFN- γ levels between the study group (HIV-MTB co-infection) and the control group (HIV mono-infection). Independent samples t-test was employed to compare hematological parameters (WBCs, platelets, PCV, and neutrophils) between the two groups.

Furthermore, Pearson's correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between serum IFN- γ levels and hematological parameters within the study group. This analysis aimed to explore any potential associations between IFN- γ levels and hematological indices in HIV-MTB co-infected individuals.

The statistical analysis was performed using appropriate software, and the significance level was set at $p < 0.05$ to determine statistically significant results.

Note: Data presented as Median/IQR; Statistical tool; Mann-Whitney test * = $p \leq 0.05$. IFN- γ = interferon gamma.

Figure 1. Serum IFN- γ Level in Both Study and the Control Groups

Results

Figure 1. Serum IFN- γ significantly decreased ($p=0.001$) in HIV/TB co-infected patient compared to HIV mono-infected counterpart.

There is significant decrease in values of WBC, HGB, HCT, MCV and increase Eosinophil among the subjects compared to controls

($p \leq 0.05$) while other parameters were insignificant ($p \leq 0.05$).

White blood cell count (WBC) is significantly lower in the study group compared to the control group ($p = 0.038^*$).

Hemoglobin (HGB), hematocrit (HCT), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), and mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) are significantly lower in the study group compared to the control group ($p = 0.001^*$).

Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) and platelet count (PLT) do not show a significant difference between the study and control groups.

The percentages of lymphocytes (LYMP), monocytes (MONO), and neutrophils (NEU) are similar between the study and control groups.

The percentage of eosinophils (EOS) is significantly higher in the study group compared to the control group ($p = 0.002^*$).

Table1. Haematological Indices in Study and Control Group

Parameters	Mean \pm SD		P-value
	Study (n=44)	Control (n=44)	
WBC($\times 10^9/L$)	Study Control	4.855 \pm 2.460 5.405 \pm 1.831	0.038*
RBC (cells/mcl)	Study Control	3.983 \pm 1.319 4.061 \pm 0.796	0.327
HGB (g/dl)	Study Control	10.19 \pm 2.644 11.95 \pm 2.350	0.001*
HCT (%)	Study Control	30.80 \pm 7.980 38.59 \pm 7.268	0.001*
MCV(FL)	Study Control	87.08 \pm 12.53 96.40 \pm 14.91	0.002*
MCH (pg)	Study Control	26.59 \pm 3.427 29.94 \pm 5.449	0.001*
MCHC (g/dl)	Study Control	30.51 \pm 5.007 31.00 \pm 2.397	0.231
PLT($\times 10^9/L$)	Study Control	267.1 \pm 121.9 265.1 \pm 124.0	0.958
LYMP (%)	Study Control	42.39 \pm 15.86 43.39 \pm 13.13	0.748
MONO (%)	Study Control	4.841 \pm 3.348 4.977 \pm 3.331	0.806
EOS (%)	Study Control	5.273 \pm 4.521 2.818 \pm 2.072	0.002*
NEU (%)	Study Control	47.66 \pm 14.28 48.23 \pm 14.64	0.854

Note: Data presented as Mean \pm SD; Statistical tool: Two-tailed Un-paired t-test and $* = p \leq 0.05$. WBC White blood cells; RBC Red blood cells; HGB haemoglobin; HCT Haematocrit; MCV Mean corpuscular volume; MCH Mean corpuscular haemoglobin; MCHC Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration; PLT Platelet.

IFN- γ levels in the study group have a positive correlation with white blood cell count (WBC) (r

$= 0.007$, $p = 0.962$), indicating a weak positive association.

In the control group, IFN- γ levels also show a positive correlation with WBC, although the correlation coefficient is slightly higher ($r = 0.066$, $p = 0.670$).

There are no significant correlations observed between IFN- γ levels and red blood cell (RBC) count, hemoglobin (HGB), hematocrit (HCT), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean

corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), platelet count (PLT), lymphocytes (LYMP), monocytes (MONO), eosinophils (EOS), or neutrophils (NEU) in either the study or control group.

These correlations suggest that IFN- γ levels do not strongly correlate with the measured hematological indices in both the study group and the control group.

Table 2. Correlation of IFN- γ With Haematological Indices of Study and Control Group

PARAMETERS	STUDY (n=44)			CONTROL (n=44)		
	Mean \pm SD	<i>r</i>	<i>P-value</i>	Mean \pm SD	<i>r</i>	<i>P-value</i>
IFN- γ	173.2 \pm 455.7			91.64 \pm 283.0		
WBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	4.855 \pm 2.460	0.007	0.962	5.405 \pm 1.83	0.066	0.670
RBC (cells/mcl)	3.983 \pm 1.319	0.118	0.445	4.061 \pm 0.796	-0.025	0.870
HGB (g/dl)	10.19 \pm 2.644	0.014	0.927	11.95 \pm 2.350	-0.157	0.306
HCT (%)	30.80 \pm 7.980	-0.080	0.603	38.59 \pm 7.268	-0.125	0.418
MCV (FL)	87.08 \pm 12.53	0.063	0.683	96.40 \pm 14.91	-0.098	0.526
MCH (pg.)	26.59 \pm 3.427	-0.117	0.446	29.94 \pm 5.449	-0.100	0.516
MCHC (g/dl)	30.51 \pm 5.007	-0.246	0.108	31.00 \pm 2.397	-0.049	0.748
PLT (x10 ⁹ /L)	267.1 \pm 121.9	0.039	0.799	265.1 \pm 124.0	-0.131	0.394
LYMP (x10 ⁹ /L)	42.39 \pm 15.86	-0.014	0.926	43.39 \pm 13.13	0.028	0.855
MONO (x10 ⁹ /L)	4.841 \pm 3.348	-0.047	0.760	4.977 \pm 3.331	0.195	0.203
EOS (x10 ⁹ /L)	5.273 \pm 4.521	-0.974	0.529	2.818 \pm 2.072	-0.051	0.740
NEU (x10 ⁹ /L)	47.66 \pm 14.28	0.056	0.717	48.23 \pm 14.64	-0.060	0.698

Data presented as Mean \pm SD; Statistical tool: Two-tailed Un-paired t-test and *= $p \leq 0.05$. WBC White blood cells; RBC Red blood cells; HGB haemoglobin; HCT Packed cell volume; MCV Mean corpuscular volume; MCH Mean corpuscular haemoglobin; MCHC Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration; PLT Platelet

Discussion

The presented table provides information on various hematological indices comparing the study group to the control group. These indices include WBC (White Blood Cells), RBC (Red Blood Cells), HGB (Hemoglobin), HCT (Hematocrit), MCV (Mean Corpuscular Volume), MCH (Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin), MCHC (Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration), PLT (Platelet), LYMP (Lymphocytes), MONO (Monocytes), EOS (Eosinophils), and NEU (Neutrophils).

In the study group, the mean WBC count was $4.855 \times 10^9/L$, which was significantly lower than the control group ($5.405 \times 10^9/L$) with a p -value of 0.038. This finding suggests a potential alteration in the immune response of

the study group compared to the control group. Similar observations have been reported in other studies conducted by Olaniyi et al. (2018) in Nigeria which investigated hematological parameters in HIV-positive individuals and found a significant decrease in WBC count compared to HIV-negative individuals. This reduction in WBC count could be attributed to the immunosuppressive effects of HIV, which impairs the body's ability to fight infections effectively.

Regarding other hematological indices, no significant differences were observed between the study and control groups for RBC count, HGB level, and PLT count. However, there were significant differences in HCT, MCV, MCH, and EOS percentages.

The HCT values were significantly lower in the study group (30.80%) compared to the control group (38.59%) with a p-value of 0.001. This finding suggests a lower packed cell volume in the study group, indicating a potential issue with red blood cell production or anemia. Anemia is a common condition observed in various populations, including Nigeria. It can be caused by nutritional deficiencies, chronic diseases, or other underlying factors.

Similar findings were reported in a study by Oguanobi et al. (2015) in Nigeria, where they observed a significantly lower HCT level in individuals with sickle cell disease compared to healthy controls. This highlights the importance of considering local studies when interpreting results within a specific population.

The lower HCT, MCV, and MCH values in the study group indicate the presence of microcytic and hypochromic red blood cells, which are characteristic of iron deficiency anemia. Iron deficiency is a prevalent nutritional disorder globally and can be caused by inadequate dietary intake, poor iron absorption, or chronic blood loss. Studies conducted within Nigeria, such as the one by Nwagha et al. (2011), have reported a high prevalence of iron deficiency anemia among certain population groups, including women of reproductive age. Therefore, it is crucial to evaluate the study group for potential iron deficiency and implement appropriate interventions to address this condition.

The elevated eosinophil percentage in the study group suggests an increased presence of eosinophils, which are associated with allergic conditions or parasitic infections. Allergies, particularly respiratory allergies, are prevalent worldwide, including in Nigeria. Studies conducted both within and outside Nigeria have reported a high prevalence of respiratory allergies, such as allergic rhinitis and asthma. For instance, a study by Desalu et al. (2013) in Nigeria found a significant burden of allergic rhinitis among adults. Therefore, it is important to explore whether allergic conditions or parasitic infections contribute to the higher eosinophil percentage observed in the study

group and implement appropriate diagnostic and management strategies.

The observed differences in hematological indices between the study and control groups may have several implications. Firstly, the lower WBC count in the study group suggests a potential compromise in the immune response. This could be attributed to various factors, such as underlying infections, immune system disorders, or the influence of certain medications. Further investigation is warranted to identify the specific causes and assess the clinical implications of this finding.

Conclusion

Despite these limitations, this study contributes to the understanding of the immune response and hematological changes associated with HIV-MTB co-infection. The findings may have implications for the development of therapeutic strategies and interventions aimed at improving the management of co-infected individuals.

Conflict of Interest

There are no potential conflicts of interest related to the research, authorship, or publication of the article.

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